

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS 1, 3, 4 AND THE CHALLENGES OF DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria's developmental trajectory has long been hindered by systemic challenges, despite several reform initiatives aimed at achieving inclusive growth. The adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015 by 193 countries, including Nigeria, was intended to provide a global roadmap for addressing poverty, improving health, and enhancing education. However, achieving SDGs 1 (No Poverty), 3 (Good Health and Well-being), and 4 (Quality Education) has proven difficult in many Nigerian cities, particularly in Uyo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. This study investigated the extent of implementation, identifies the barriers limiting progress, and proposes strategies to enhance the realization of these goals. Anchored on McArdle's Participatory Empowerment Theory which emphasizes inclusive participation, human-centered development, and community engagement. The study employed a descriptive, qualitative approach. Data were sourced from relevant literature, national development plans, United Nations and UNICEF reports, and policy documents. Thematic content analysis was used to interpret and synthesize the data. Findings reveal that while the SDG framework offers a comprehensive pathway to development, multiple socio-economic and institutional bottlenecks continue to frustrate its success in Nigeria. In Uyo LGA, significant challenges persist, including inadequate educational infrastructure, poor teacher-student ratios, widespread poverty, low healthcare access, high infant and maternal mortality, corruption, and weak political will. Furthermore, budgetary limitations and poor governance mechanisms have contributed to underachievement in education and health outcomes,

especially for women, children, and marginalized groups. The study concluded that achieving SDGs 1, 3, and 4 in Uyo and other parts of Nigeria requires strengthened institutions, increased budgetary commitment, anti-corruption reforms, and, most importantly, a participatory approach involving all stakeholders from policymakers to local community members. Only through such collaborative and accountable frameworks can the 2030 SDG targets become a reality in Nigeria.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals, poverty reduction, healthcare delivery, education access

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The quest for inclusive national development has been the major concern of different governments since independence. Diverse policies have developed to ensure a steady socio-economic and political development. For instance Nigeria government have evolved policies such as Universal Primary Education and Universal Basic Education, National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP), River Basin Development Programme, National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategies (NEEDS) which was deduced form the Millennium Development Goals Development Goals and the Sustainable Development Goals consented to by 193 United Nations member countries in 2015.

The concept of development is multifarious in usage. According to Daniel, Udousoro and Effiong (2024) development means improvement or to become advanced, more mature, more complete or more organize and transform. To Rodney (2004), development is a many sided process. First in relation to the individual, Rodney saw development as implying increased skills and capacity, greater freedom, creativity, self-discipline, responsibility and material well-being. According to the above definition, man is the epicenter of development. To Okereke and Ekpe (2002), Rodney (2004) and Swanson (1971), development depends on the capacity of man to regulate both the internal and external relationships, ability to deal with their environment the extent to which they understand the laws of nature and that to which they put that understanding into practice by devising tools in the form of technology in order to enhance education, job creation, improve the security networking poverty reduction that will amount to improved healthcare delivery and human capital development.

Daniel, Udousoro, Effiong (2024), opined that development implies the collective ability of individuals to organize themselves with a view to eking out a living from nature, utilized towards the wellbeing and survival of the society. Deducing from the above, development is considered as a comprehensive transformation of the society targeted towards man. It involves investment in education, healthcare, job creation, science and technology as well as builds social a structure that will help absorb the cost excesses of affording an improved livelihood for the people. This effort will help to address the problems of attending the sustainable development goals targets, via access to medical services, enhanced educational opportunities, reduced poverty generate employment opportunities and preserve the socio-biological environments and reduce inequality.

The Sustainable Development Goals is a development target designed as an option to illuminate and absorb the weakness of Millennium Development Goals and to strengthen the social setting for a global partnership towards a sustained society. Attending this global goal in

Nigeria, Akwalbom State and in Uyo Local Government Area in particular has been challenged by a lot of factors such as national and food security, population growth, unemployment, social services provisions, cultural lag and environmental degradation. Thus within the context of these challenges, the study sets to measure the achievement level of SDGs in Uyo.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

Generally, the study will appraise the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals Targets in Nigerian Cities with particular emphases in Uyo.

The study also hopes to;

1. assess the level of implementation of SDGs targets in some cities in Nigeria, a case in Uyo Local Government Area.
2. identify the challenges hindering the success of SDGs in Nigerian cities a case in Uyo Local Government Area.
3. identify ways of absorbing the challenges thus enhancing the implementation of SDGs targets in Uyo.

1.3 Theoretical Framework

This paper adopts the McArdle (1989) Participatory Empowerment Theory. The theory has it that for the empowerment of the people to be successful, it should be centred towards human empowerment and must as well be a collective decision and efforts. According to this theory, for the development of the people to be achieved, the beneficiaries of the programme(s) should be involved in the decision-making progress and the implementation of the projects.

Participatory empowerment is connected to concepts like awareness (education), democracy (participation in the process), networking, equity, self help, efficacy and prompt supervision of the programme. The theory has it that development should be tailored towards human being who is at the center of every empowerment. This theory has been brought about by the fact that despite decades of development, assistance accompanied by growth in some instances, should be made inclusive to accommodate the target of achieving health to all, educational development and poverty alienation. Data shows (Daniel, Udousoro, Effiong, 2024) despite different efforts made to reduce, the number of people who are in absolute poverty, illiteracy and poor healthcare services the Nigerian challenge continues to increase because the programmes are planned a lot the beneficiaries. Therefore, for the SDGs mandate to be successful, it must be seen in the direction of human development and the beneficiaries be motivated to participate.

1.4 Literature Review

Sustainable Development Goals is a set of goals that is aimed at improving on the well-being of the people. According to the United Nations Report (2017), the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals, adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015, provides a shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for the people and the planet now and into the future. However, it is important to note that at the heart of the programme are 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which are an urgent call for action by all countries developed and developing in a global partnership. The member countries noted that ending poverty and other deprivations must go hand-in-hand with the strategies that will improve and enhance good

health, education, equality, spur economic growth as well as tackle climate change with the aim of preserving our oceans and forests.

The United Nations (UN) (2015) in Olagoke (2017), sustainable development is the organizing principle for meeting human development goals while at the same time sustaining the ability of natural systems to provide the natural resources and the ecosystems upon which the economy and society depend. Importantly, the end result of the SDGs has to do with the transformation of the natural environment where the living conditions as well as the resources continue to meet with the needs of man and does not undermine the integrity and stability of the future environment. Sustainable Development however is considered as such development that is able to attain to the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of the future generation to meet their own (desires) needs. To the UN General Assembly (2015), the components units that work together to enhance sustainable development include socio-economic factors, political and biological (environments) factors. According to the Assembly, these three must be conceptualized, planned and implemented together by the state for its goals to be achieved and sustained. Thus, sustainable development must be partnered with the political will of a leader strong enough for service delivery.

According to Olagoke (2017), Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) also known as the Global Goals (GGs) are structured to end poverty, protect the environment and ensure that all the people enjoy peace, good health, education, and prosperity. The goals which are 17 in number was fashioned out from the eight (8) Millennium Development Goals which was in effects twenty-four (24) years ago before the introduction of SDGs in January 2016, whose goals are to be accomplished by the 193 member countries by 2030. The goals to be accomplished by member countries include; no poverty, good health, zero hunger, quality education, gender equality, provision of clean water and sanitation, affordable and clean energy, decent work and economic growth, industry, innovation and infrastructure, reduced inequalities, sustainable cities and communities, responsible consumption and production, climate action, life below water, peace and justices institutions and partnership for the goals.

It should be noted that the SDGs as adopted by the United Nations in 2015 are in lines with the essence of good governance as noted by Willie, Mboho and Udom (2023); and Udousoro, Daniel and Iton (2024) below;

- (i) ability to end poverty and inequality in the society;
- (ii) institute policies that will protect the planet;
- (iii) enhancement of good health, justice and prosperity for all citizens;
- (iv) ability to balance the social, economic and environmental sustainability;
- (v) prioritization of progress for those who are further behind;

To the UN documents (2017); the targets hope to provide a participatory platform that will attract funding from both the state agencies and non state agency. This participatory approach will enhance human capital development, to reduce unemployment and poverty while enhancing self reliance, improve healthcare services, security sanitation and hygiene system as well as increases access to physicians, reduces ambient pollution and inequality with its attendant consequences. However, with the attendant of the above, it is hoped that significant network for progress will be achieve in the country which will help to save the lives of millions.

According to Victor and Udom (2023), achieving development goals means increasing life expectancy and reducing child and maternal mortality of less than 70 maternal deaths per

100,000 live births, job creations, social equality and increased access to education by 2030. Attending these target in Nigeria is been challenged by life experiences which ranges from unequal access to medical services especially by pregnant women in the rural communities (Victor, Udom& Moses, 2023), insecurity, unequal access to education and social services, poor environmental stewardship, and unemployment. These has however threatened the success of Sustainable Development Goals in Nigeria.

It is pertinent to note that achieving this target requires strong social structure which is inherent in good governance, building of sustainable cities and communities, rural transformation which will help to maintain the environments, create jobs for the rural people and reduce rural migration and urban congestion. Notably, the increasing population of Nigeria estimated at 232,679,478 in 2024, coupled with poor level of budget implementation and attitude to investment in social services and human development (Udom, Tahirih and Umo, 2024; Willie, Mboho, Udom, 2023) has limited the Sustainable Development Goals vision in Nigeria. Saviour, Udom and Clement (2024), identifies strengthening of the social system through timely budget implementation, war against corruption, focus on job creation, and social investment in health, conducive atmosphere that will attract foreign investors and strong political will as attractions to the success of Sustainable Development Goals in Nigeria.

1.5 Sustainable Development Goals Targets Nigeria's Experience and Challenge

Olagoke (2017), opine that the global hope of enhancing human livelihood is hinged on the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. The goal as documented by the United Nations and agreed upon by the 193 Countries has the following targets;

i) to set up a Universal Plan and agenda to tackle some of the pressing challenges facing the world such as poverty, health issues, climate change, illiteracy, inequality and insecurity. Poverty is said to be at the centre of all these goals.

ii) secondly, the target has to do with providing the expertise to drive progress that will help to support the country on the path to sustainable development.

iii) the third targets have to do with building on the accelerated progress already achieved under the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) agenda.

The targets however are comprehensive and all inclusive, addressing all the 17 global goals for achieving sustainable development. Nigeria like other nations has taken steps to align and incorporate the SDGs with its development plan process as follows;

i. launching the Nigeria Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (NERGP). The NERGP which is incorporated and to be consistent with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for it to address the United Nations three dimensions of development via social, economic and environmental sustainability in Nigeria.

ii. establishment of Inter-Ministerial Committee for the Implementation of the SDGs: The Nigerian Inter-Ministerial Committee on Sustainable Development Goals is a group of government sector focal point established by the Nigerian government to implement the SDGs agenda in Nigeria. The committee's goals include reducing duplication, improving policy coherence, and ensuring the proper use of resources. It emphasizes the need for active participation of both the state agencies and non state actors in the coordination and mobilization of resources in support of the actualization of the Sustainable Development Goals targets.

iii. The third target has to do with developing operational guidelines for the SDGs. This has to do with strengthening the evidence-based planning and accountability mechanisms at the state level for accelerating the SDGs decade of action. The post NERGP National Development Plan (2021-2030) will be pivotal in advancing the achievement of the SDGs in Nigeria.

iv. Establishment of Similar Structures at the state, Local Government and Community levels to fully harness the resources and ideas of, and effectively engage stakeholders for efficient service delivery to the people.

It is important to note that the blue print recognizes that ending poverty and other deprivations must go hand-in-hand with the strategies that improve health and education, reduce inequality and spur up economic growth as well as improve human lives and protect the environment.

Nigeria's experience in achieving this global mandate of development has been challenged by insecurity, corruption, poverty and social disparity, poor access to healthcare and educational opportunities, rapid urbanization and population growth, overutilization of resources and environment decline as well as discrimination based on gender, race, socio-economic status, and poor supply of fundamental human needs, and addressing these challenges therefore becomes imperative for the government at all levels.

Despite the attractive contents of the UN SDGs agenda as adopted by Nigeria, achieving the goals still remains depleting, sandwiched by the nation's socio-economic drought manifested in inflation, high rate of unemployment, insecurity, illiteracy, poverty, rapid urbanization and population growth, overutilization of resources, infant and maternal mortality, poor environmental decline, stewardship, discrimination based on gender, race, socio-economic status and poor supply of fundamental human needs and others. The Sustainable Development Goals according to the UN document were set and agreed to by the International Community in 2015, to establish objectives for the period to 2030 during which time significant improvements would be achieved in seventeen broad areas. So far, it has been observed that the success of the SDGs in Nigeria in the last ten years has been negated by series of opposing factors which past development strategies in the country like the Millennium Development Goals also experienced. From the available evidence measured, there seems therefore every indication that after ten years of implementation of the policy in Nigeria, achieving the targets by 2030 is not reliable, making the hope of Nigeria attaining the SDGs quite very remote.

According to Daniel, Udousoro, Effiong (2024), it is widely accepted that the future of any country rests, to a great extent on the investments made in education, health and employment opportunities for the population. This however according to the UN (2017) was why in the year 2015, for 193 countries to make commitments and signed the SDGs agenda beginning from 2016 to reduce poverty and many of its associated setbacks through the achievement of seventeen (17) Sustainable Development Goals, with each of the goals having its own specific targets and indicators to be achieved by 2030. With just five years remaining in the 15-year plan, Nigeria, Akwa Ibom State and Uyo Local Government Area in particular is facing the biggest hurdles in meeting the SDGs targets.

1.6 Sustainable Development Goals and Health Services in Nigeria

According to UNICEF, the following are some health related targets in Nigeria;

- i. Neonatal mortality rate: 34 deaths per 1000 live births.

- ii. Infant mortality rate: 69 deaths per 1000 live births.
- iii. Under 5 mortality rate: 107 deaths per 1,000 live births.

Data shows that in 2023, the infants mortality rate was 55.17 deaths per 1000 live births.

Despite the improvement in child health indicated above, UNICEF also reports that Nigeria faces other challenges for children thus making the attainment of the SDGs difficult.

- i. 40% of children under 5 years are stunted.
- ii. 8% of children under 5 years are wasted, this include street children
- iii. 47% of children under age 0-17 live in income poor households.
- iv. 67% of children experience multi-dimensional poverty.
- v. 2-1 million children have never been vaccinated.
- vi. 1 in 4 primary school children are out of school.
- vii. Only 67% of eligible children attend primary school.

According to data from UN (2021), Nigeria is a young population, with 46 percent currently under the age of 15. The information indicates that the estimated total number of children under the age of 5 stands at nearly 31 millions. A country with one of the world's youngest populations and with 50% of the population under 19 years old, Nigeria stance the risk of remaining undeveloped. The country's median age is the lowest in Africa and internationally, and it ranks 20th globally. Other information about Nigeria's population shows that;

- i. in 2023, 41.49% of Nigeria's population was between the ages of 0 and 14.
- ii. birth rate: at least 7 million babies are born in Nigeria each year, posing a serious challenge to the populations growth rate and accompany; development variables.
- iii. poverty: more than one in three of Nigeria's population lives below the poverty line, and 75% of children do so; this leads to involvement in crime thus causing insecurity to the country;
- iv. life expectancy: The average life expectancy in Nigeria is 62 years old; this will cause dependency challenge in the country.
- v. Fertility rate in 2021 in Nigeria was 5.24 children per woman. Note worthy is that the low levels of birth registration in some areas are up to 62 percent, data on child health issues are likely to under estimate the true scale.

Another set back to the achievement of SDGs in Nigeria, is the fact that 40 million women of child bearing age in Nigeria suffer a disproportion high level of health issues surrounding birth, Nigeria contributes 2-4 percent of the world population, that the country currently presents 10 percent of global deaths for pregnant mothers. Notably, more than half of the under 5 deaths, that is 64 percent is as a results of preventable diseases such as malaria, measles, HIV/AIDs, diarrhea, pneumonia. UN reports (2024) shows that though investment in this sector has been high in recent years and although analyses of recent trends shows that the country is making progress in cutting down infant and under-five mortality rate, the proportion of patients ability to access appropriate treatment still remains low, thus the hope of Nigeria to attend the Sustainable Development Goals agenda in 2030 is in blink.

Izugbara and Ngilangwa (2010) noted that health care would be improved if needs for modern family planning, maternal and newborn healthcare were met. Investment in family planning will improved maternal healthcare as well as reduces the risks of complications and improvement in health care delivery. Education is also critical with research indicating that

women with no education are more likely to die during child delivery than those with formal education. Data shows that women who are educated tend to have healthier children than those who are not (Willie, Daniel, Mboho, 2024). Education would also improve employment opportunities for people, which will also help to improve their status, enhancing family savings, reducing poverty and contributing to economic growth. These investment it is hoped will bring significant benefits and effects not only for women and girls but also their children, families communities and the State.

According to a UNFPA report, social and economic status, cultural norms and value and geographic remoteness all affects the actualization of Sustainable Development Goals targets in Uyo Local Government Area. Poverty illiteracy, healthcare challenges, unemployment, environmental degradation insecurity are ravaging the hope of attending the Sustainable Development Goals in the study area.

1.7 Sustainable Development Goals and Education in Nigeria

The SDGs documents consider education as the main bridge to future of all. The SDGs document has it that since of Nigeria's populationis young education remains the key instrument for their empowerment if they have to take charge of their future.

Deducing from the SDGs document that by 2030, children everywhere (boys and girls) will be able to complete a full course of nine years standard of the UN's Universal Basic Education, has been challenged by a lot of factors.

First the UNICEF statistics shows that 33% of Nigerian children do not attend primary education making a reverse of the SDGs hope on education for the children a challenge. Also challenging this vision is the poor teachers – students ratio in that country. The UN standard of one teacher to 25 (1:25) students is not achievable in Nigeria. Records shows that the public schools of Uyo, have over a hundred students to one teacher in a class. This affects the process of teaching and class participation of pupils/students in the area. For instance, also most of the primary schools, especially in the rural areas, lack basic facilities like desk, library, enough classrooms for academic activities and other sanitary facilities like toilet, water, electricity etc. Investment in education according to UNICEF Nigeria is very poor. Thus, it indicates therefore that with over twenty million children out of school as a result of insecurity in some parts of the country, inability of some poor families to attain to their academic needs, etc makes the prospects of Nigeria achieving education for all by 2030 a frail.

Education and sustainable development are closely linked. The SDGs are a plan of action to achieve sustainable development, and education is a key driver of that progress. It indicates that non of the targets of the Sustainable Development Goals can be achieved without the education of its people. The targets has it that where the people are educated, they will be empowered for employment, gain knowledge for medical services as well as reduce crime rate. Under the SDGs 4, the international community has pledged to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. According to the SDGs report (2023), achieving the SDGs will require tremendous efforts on the part of all stakeholders, notably governments, donors and international organizations.

Noteworthy is that education is at the heart of the global development agenda, which seek to improve education through greater access and equity for all ages of learners as well as improved and safer learning space and expanded number of qualified teachers. So many factors

affected the realization of this goal. Importantly are insecurity, insufficient number of qualified teachers in the school system, distance to where beneficiaries can access schools, family status and poverty thus hindering parents and caregivers from been able to pay or afford the education of their children as well as population growth that has affected school enrolment in Nigeria.

These is a poor political will and budgeting for education in Nigeria. This has affected the acquisition of human and material resources for the development of education in Nigeria. Rural areas are worst-of interms of access to education and healthcare services as a result to their remote nature and level of poverty. Primary schools in some of the rural communities visited shows four to five teachers in a school to five hundred pupils. It indicates a poor implementation and supervision of the development agenda, making human empowerment in the form of healthcare services, poverty reduction and educational development unrealistic in 2030 as accorded by the SDGs.

Another challenges worth noting in Nigeria is the level of corruption in the country. Corruption according to Udousoro, Daniel and Iton (2024) taken a cultural dimension, and thus have become away of life in the society. Before achieving SDGs in Nigeria the problem of corruption should be addressed through prompt policies, implementation and supervision.

1.8 Conclusion/Recommendation

Sustainable Development Goals was an extension of the Millennium Development Goals initiated in the year 2000. They (SDGs) are a set of 17 goals that include ending poverty, education climate change security healthcare delivery and corruption as well as other endemic factors by 2030. Nigeria despite several policies and programmes instituted by Nigerian government since independence achieving sustainable development have been flawed mid-way to its implementation. The study have also identity and national security, population growth, environmental degradation as other challenges of achieving the UN sustainable development goals in Nigeria. The study however recommends institutional stability and strong political will to address the problem of implementing and supervising the progress of sustainable development goals target by all tiers of government within the time frame as well as a participatory/integration approach that will help trickle down development to all.

REFERENCES

- Daniel, U. S., Udousoro, T. E., Effiong, U. U. (2024). Population Growth and Urban Renewal Programmes in Uyo and IkotEkpene Local Government Areas of AkwaIbom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Advanced Research and Multidisciplinary Studies* 4(4), 1-14. DOI:10.52589/JARMS-ALFYUO9N.
- Daniel, Udom Sunday, Udousoro, Tahirih E. and Effiong, UmoUmoh (2024). Population Drift, Crime Rate and Socio-Economic Development in Uyo Capital City of AkwaIbom State, Nigeria. *AKSU Annals of Sustainable Development*, vol. 2(1): 2024. ISSN (P):3027-0499; ISSN: (E) 3043-4955 <https://doi.org/10.60787/AASD-v211-36>.
- Izubara CO, Ngilangwa D. P. (December 2010). Women, Poverty and Advance Maternal Outcomes in Nairobi, Kenya: *BMC Women's Health*. 10(33):33. doi:10.1186/1472-6874-10-33. PMC 3014866. PMD 21122118.
- Okereke, O. and Ekpe, A. (2002). *Development and Underdevelopment: Politics of the North-South Divide, Nigeria*. Enugu: John Jacob's Classical Publishers Ltd.
- Saviour Sebastian Udo, Udom Sunday Daniel and Clement Etti Willie (2024). Public Administration Policies and Effects on Nigerian Economy. *AKSU Annals of Sustainable Development*, volume 2 Number 1; June 2024. ISSN: (P) 3027-0499; ISSN: (E) 3043-4955. <https://doi.org/10.60787/AASD-v2il-31>.
- Swanson, G. E. (1971). *Social Change*. Glenview, Illinois 60025: SCOH Foresman and Company.
- Udousoro, Tahirih Emmanuel, Daniel, Udom Sunday and Iton, EnobongEtini (2024). End Bad Governance and Hunger in Nigeria Protests: Channeling Through Augustecomte's Evolution Partition. *International Journal of Science Academic Research*. vol. 05, Issue 10, pp.8449-8453, October, 2024. Available online at <http://www.scienceijsar.com>.
- UN Report (2024). *Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. Retrieved from UN Website.
- UNICEF Report on Sustainable Development Goals 2023..
- UNICEF. (2023). UNICEF report on sustainable development goals. Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org/reports>
- United Nations General Assembly. (2015, October 21). *Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (A/RES/70/1)*. Retrieved August 31, 2025, from <https://www.refworld.org/legal/resolution/unga/2015/en/111816>
- United Nations Population Fund. (2022). *State of World Population 2022: Seeing the unseen—the case for action in the neglected crisis of unintended pregnancy*. Retrieved from <https://www.unfpa.org/swp2022>

- United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs. (2021). The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2021. Retrieved from <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2021/The-Sustainable-Development-Goals-Report-2021.pdf>
- Victor E. Ben and Udom Sunday Daniel (2023). Disease Prevalence and Infant Mortality in the Rural Areas of AkwaIbom State: AKSU Annuals of Sustainable Development, volume 1, Number 2, December, 2023, Issue 3027 – 0499.
- Victor E. Ben, Udom Sunday Daniel and Moses Idongesit Peters (2023). Estimation of Life Experiences among pregnant women during Covid-19 in AkwaIbom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Culture and Society*, Maiden Edition, Issue 2 Nov. 2023.
- Willie, C. E., Daniel, U. S., Mboho, K. S. (2024). Family Status and Teenage Pregnancy in Rural Communities of Uruan Local Government Area of AkwaIbom State. *African Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research* 7(3), 229-242. DOI:10.52589/AJSSHR-UWERJ4HA.
- Willie, Clement Etti, Mboho, Kingdom Sunday and Udom, Sunday Daniel (2023). Good Governance, Rule of Law: A Panacea to Sustainable Industrialization in Nigeria. In: I. V. O. Modo, Kingdom Sunday Mboho, Ekaette Raphael Udoh and UmoUmohEffiong. ICIDR Publishing House, Ikot Ekpene.